

THE ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This article describes the role of entrepreneurship in economic development. In Uzbekistan, the socio-economic relations of the entrepreneurial society are embodied, clearly manifested, and are becoming a rapidly developing and dynamic field. Its place and role in the formation of market relations and economic development in the country is becoming more and more significant. We know that the main source of income of the developed countries of the world is business.

Key words: entrepreneurship, entrepreneur, services, technologies, economy

Introduction

The first scientific studies on entrepreneurship were carried out by the great scholars of the 18th century, R. Cantilon, A. Turgot, F. Kene, A. Smith, J. B. Sey and others. Therefore, the emergence of the concepts of "entrepreneur" and "entrepreneurship" corresponds to this period. Later, such research expanded and took on the appearance of a separate scientific direction, and the practical application of their results began to show an effective effect on the economy. One of such results is the definition and enrichment of the concept of "entrepreneurship".

Schumpeter hypothesizes that economic development is a process consisting of stages of harmonization of production factors. This means that each new combination of production factors is a stage of economic development. Only an entrepreneur is capable of implementing such new combinations. Because he was an innovator, creator, inventor, he created a new harmony, that is, mastering the production of previously unknown benefits, new sources of raw materials, new technology, perfect systems of production organization and management, strives for success and achieves it. That is why the entrepreneur occupies a central place in the development and modernization of the economic horse. Therefore, entrepreneurial innovation is related to the creation of new goods, services, technologies, methods, and is able to bring economic efficiency to a completely new level.

In Uzbekistan, entrepreneurship is showing its creative, reforming and innovative power in the socio-economic development of the country and is

taking a place accordingly. Of course, it is not easy to completely transition from one socio-economic system to another, it is necessary to solve many contradictions and problems. Moreover, entrepreneurship is being formed as a multifaceted, multifaceted, multifaceted complex system. Scientific analysis of such a complex system and its problems and finding solutions should be a continuous scientific and educational process. Currently, the main science that studies the field of entrepreneurship, its activities, relationships, and problems is the basics of entrepreneurship. So, entrepreneurship is an object of the science of the basics of entrepreneurship, but this science has not yet taken a proper place in the economic sciences. Its purpose should be in accordance with the purpose and role of entrepreneurship in the socio-economic system and development of the country: This requires that a wider place be given to the study and teaching of this subject.

In the early stages of the development of countries where the market economy did not exist, the growth of ideas about entrepreneurship was considered to be the most important characteristic of management skills, and the activity of a manager is more important than the role of an innovator. But the transition to a high-tech economy brings out such an interpretation of entrepreneurship, which is mainly related to innovation processes and their dissemination on the basis of their own innovations or on the basis of involvement in innovative innovation. Accordingly, imitative entrepreneurship is of great importance in the economic development of a country with an agrarian economy and in the first stage of industrialization. It is based on technology that involves the use of available and easily available resources, management skills, and technical knowledge. We believe that it is necessary to study the thoughts, opinions, views on business activity and concept, and analyze them in depth in order to add certain clarifications to them. It is known that entrepreneurial activity and the concept that reflects it are multifaceted and complex phenomena. Therefore, it is necessary to determine their essence according to their separate sides, edges, and directions. First of all, we will look at the general and concrete levels of the concept of entrepreneurship. At the general level of entrepreneurship, it is necessary to distinguish between its two states - static and dynamic states. Entrepreneurship appears as an approach in a static state, and as a process and activity in a dynamic state. Entrepreneurship is an approach that consists in finding and using opportunities to improve existing methods of doing work and to use new ones. This approach, unlike the traditional approach, includes active

elements such as curiosity, creative steps, and initiative. Entrepreneurship is a process, an activity, an entrepreneurial approach to the goal set.

Entrepreneurship is important to raise production to a new, higher level in terms of quality by restructuring production, combining and organizing production factors (labor, labor tools, labor objects) in a new harmony, and more effectively coordinating production relations with productive forces. contributes. This creates new, additional opportunities for the implementation and development of production, and their implementation ensures the increase in productivity of existing capacities, the production of additional products and the increase in efficiency. Entrepreneurship actively involves the previously unused population savings, local resources, production and household waste, and foreign investments into the socio-economic process, leading to the expansion of production, increase of national product and wealth. Entrepreneurship is not only a source of personal income, but also a significant source of income for the state. A large part of the state budget revenues falls on the business sector. Therefore, entrepreneurship plays a major role in filling the budget, increasing the power of the state, and providing funds for social and economic development. Thus, entrepreneurship plays an important role in improving the life and well-being of the population, its cultural and spiritual development, raising the country's production, export, economic potential, strengthening its independence, and socio-economic development.

Entrepreneurship has developed significantly in Uzbekistan and has reached a certain level in its development. After the independence of Uzbekistan, great attention was paid to the liberalization of the economy and trade, the creation of various forms of property, and the development of competition. It was recognized that entrepreneurship plays an important role in the solution of these issues and, in general, in the social and economic development of the country, and the creation of necessary conditions for the formation and promotion of entrepreneurship in the republic was started. First of all, the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan recognized entrepreneurship and paved the way for its formation and development. On February 15, 1991, the first law "On Entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan" was adopted and it served as the main legal basis for entrepreneurship. Later, the necessary changes and additions were made to this law, it was improved a lot, and it was supplemented and strengthened by a number of other laws and decisions, statutory legal documents. In the development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, the increase of economic freedom and the reduction of

administrative and legal restrictions, the state support of entrepreneurship (first of all, small, private, joint entrepreneurship), the opening of new opportunities and areas of entrepreneurial initiative, tax reforms and administrative reforms have also helped greatly. In the country, the capital market and business funding opportunities have expanded, new financial institutions and information provision have developed, the patent-licensing system has been strengthened, new types of economic activity have appeared and are expanding. Necessary conditions have been created for faster establishment and development of entrepreneurship in the republic, and for it to take its rightful place in the society, and they continue to be improved. The most important of them and the basis for other conditions is the legal framework. This base is expanding, strengthening, improving and developing year by year.

In conclusion, we can say that in the current era of globalization, countries with underdeveloped economies remain dependent on other large countries. In order to prevent it, many countries started to develop their business sector. In particular, the business sector is developing rapidly in Uzbekistan. Previously, semi-finished products were sold abroad, but now the production of finished products, that is, the cluster system, has also been revolutionized. In the development of the economy, industries such as entrepreneurship and delivery are dependent on each other. Taking into account such problems, countries are building their own transport routes.

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